

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Futbolchilarni texnik va taktik tayyorgarligi.

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Anotatsiya

Futbolchilarning o'yindagi asosiy elementlaridan biri xisoblangan ularning texnik va taktik tayyorgarligidir. Texnik va taktik tayyorgarlik asosan o'yinchilarga jismoniy va aqliy sifatlarini birlashgan natijalari yuzasidan namoyon bo'ladi.

-Texnik tayyorgarligi-bu futbolchilarning to'pni oshirish, olib yurish, to'xtatish, zarbalar berish kabi sifatlarining jamlanmasidir.

-Taktik tayyorgarlik esa bu futbolchilarni o'yin davomida murabbiy tamonidan berilgan maydondagi vazifalarining bajarilishidir.

Kalit so'zlar: Futbol, texnika, taktika, tayyorgarlik, maydon, to'p, tezkorlik, jamoa, hujum, darvoza

Kirish

Futbolchilarni texnik va taktik tayyorgarligini to'psiz va to'p bilan amalga oshirilib bunda asosan yugurishlar, yurishlar, sakrashlar, to'xtashlar va burilishlar uning asosini tashkil etadi. Futbolchilar maydonda asosan asosiy o'yin o'ynash holatlarini turish-yugurish, almashinib yugurish, harakatni tezda o'zgartirish, yo'nalish tezligini har-xilligi joydan va yugurib kelib balandga sakrash, o'z gavda og'irligi bir oyog'idan ikkinchisiga tezda almashtirish, tezda to'xtash va joydan tezkor chiqib ketish, start tezligini oshirish, joyidan va yugurib ketayotib to'xtash va burilishlar shular jumlasiga kiradi.. Yakka tartibda texnik va taktik tayyorgarligi bu har bir futbolchi shu texnik holatlarni mukammal egallagan bo'lishi shartdir. Taktik tayyorgarligida esa murabbiy tamonidan berilgan vazifalarni to'liq bajarishi lozim.

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1) har bir maydonda o'ynayotgan futbolchi oyoqlarida va boshida kelayotgan to'pni, yumalab va xavodan kelayotgan to'pni, har xil balandlikda, har xil tezlikda, to'g'ri, aniq va kuchli zarba bilan yo'naltirish, darvozaga hamda jamoadoshlariga yetkazib berishi; 2) oyoqlarida to'pni to'xtatishlari, kelayotgan to'pni xavodan, yumalab, tezkor, burmalatib uchishda to'xtatishlari; 3) to'pni olib yurish davomida yo'nalishini tezda o'zgartirish, tezligini almashtirishi harakatlari; 4) raqibidan to'pni egallab olishda to'pni oshirish paytida, to'pni qabul qilishi paytida ham to'pni olib yurishi davomidagi harakatlari; 5) to'pni maydonga avutdan tashlash; 6) aldamchi harakatlari darvozaga zarba berishidagi, to'pni jamoadoshiga oshirishdagi, to'pni olib yurishi paytidagi hamda to'pni egallash paytidagi harakatlari texnika harakatlari yig'indisi bo'lib xisoblanadi.

Futbolchilar mana shu texnik harakatlarni mukammal egallagan bo'lishlari shartdir. To'pga zarba berishdagi texnik harakatlari ham shu futbolchining zarbadagi texnik ko'rsatkichlarini belgilaydi. Ayniqsa bu ko'rsatkich xujumchilarning o'ng va chap oyoqlarini bir xil zarbalar kuchini belgilaydi. To'pni xavodagi uchish tezligi, bu oyoqning tezkor harakatining kuchli oyoqdagi siltanishining tezligiga bog'liqdir va shu oyoqning qattiq qismi bilan zarba berishligidadir. To'g'ri zarba berish esa to'pning o'rta qismiga zarba berishdadir.

Futbolchining taktik tayyorgarligi esa murabbiy tomonidan qo'yilgan o'z ampulasidagi vazifani bajarishidadir. Maydonda futbolchining vazifalari tez-tez o'zgarib turadi, ya'ni to'p bilan jamoadoshlari xujum uyushtirgan paytida u xujumchi vazifasini bajarsa, raqib jamoasi to'pni egallab olganda ximoyachi vazifasini bajarishi kerak bo'ladi. Futbolchilar maydonda murabbiy tomonidan qo'yilgan taktik tizimi, asosida o'z vazifalarini bajarishi kerak. Maydonda o'ynayotgan futbolchi doimo o'z vazifalarini butun o'yin davomida o'zgartirib turishiga to'g'ri keladi. Futbolchilar butun o'yin davomida individual, guruhlariga va

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jamo'a bo'lib ham ximoyada ham hujumda taktik tizimi asosida o'z vazifalarini bajaradilar. Hozirgi zamon futbolida butun dunyo mamlakatlari o'z taktik tizimi asosida mashg'ulotlar olib bormoqdalar.

Bu tizimlardan eng asosiylari 4-2-4 (to'rtta ximoyachi, ikki yarim ximoyachi to'rtta hujumchi) 1-4-3-2 (bitta tayanch ximoyachi, to'rtta ximoyachi, uchta yarim himoyachi, ikkita hujumchi) 4-3-3; 1-3-3-3; 1-3-2-4 kabi taktik tizimlarda harakat qiladilar. Darvozabon o'yinda eng asosiy vazifani bajaruvchi hisoblanadi. Uning asosiy vazifasini o'z darvozasidan to'p qo'yib yubrmalik, qolaversa butun o'yin davomida jamoadoshlariga yaqindan yordam berish kerakdir. Darvozabon asosan, chaqqon, epchil, raqib o'yin taktikasini yaxshi o'qiy oladigan, ishonchli o'ziga ishongan, tez harakatchan, hamda jamoadoshlari bilan kelisha oladigan bo'lishi kerak. Bundan tashqari u to'p ushlash, to'p urib yuborish, ilib olish, to'pni o'yinga kiritish, tezkor hujum uyushtirish, qulay vaziyatda turgan raqibini ko'ra bilish va jamoadoshlariga ko'rsatmalar berishi bilan ajralib turadi. Darvozabon texnik tayyorgarligiga quyidagilar kiradi:

- 1) darvozabonni turish harakatlari;
- 2) to'pni ilib olishi yerdan yoki xavodan;
- 3) to'pni urib yuborish;
- 4) to'pni egallab olishi, o'ng va chap qanotga yetkazib berishi;
- 5) to'pni o'yinga kiritish usullari.

Xulosa

Futbol bu- eng ommaviy sport turlaridan hisoblanib harakat qobiliyatlari va texnik tayyorgarligini oshirishni ta'minlaydigan sport turidir, jismoniy va texnik tayyorgarlik darajasini oshirish uchun o'yin usullarini shakllantirish va muvofiqlashtirish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga birgalikda ta'sir qilish vositalarini joriy etish zarur. Futbolchining taktik tayyorgarligi sport o'yinlarida mashg'ulot jarayonini takomillashtirishning asosiy usullaridan biri bu yo'naltirilgan jismoniy

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faollikdir mehnat qobiliyati va almashinuv jarayonlariga o'ziga xos ta'sir ko'rsatadigan kuch, tezlik, chidamlilik (aerob va anaerob) namoyon bo'lishi bilan bog'liq. Jismoniy tayyorgarlik har bir tanada qancha yuqori bo'lsa natijaga erishish shuncha oson bo'ladi.

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